

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE DIMENSIONAL STABILITY OF THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITES BY SPECKLE PATTERN INTERFEROMETRY

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ABSTRACT

Electronic speckle pattern interferometry (ESPI), a full-field method which provides a means for measuring displacements in three dimensions in the sub-micron range without contacting the sample, is used for the study of the long-term deformation behavior of fiber-reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites. Examples of the relaxation of warpage-causing stresses in unbalanced cross-ply laminates are presented. The results show the importance of structural stiffness and viscoelastic effects in determining the dimensional stability. It is shown that the geometry of the part is as important as the intrinsic material properties themselves. The observed deformations subject the material to a mixed mode of creep and relaxation.

Keywords: Dimensional stability, interferometry, internal stresses, viscoelastic behavior

1. INTRODUCTION

The dimensional stability of a material is its capacity to maintain a given geometry. This capacity is not an intrinsic property of the material. The shape and structure of a part, the constraints applied to it, the processing influences and the environmental influences during its lifetime may have a large impact on its dimensional stability. Factors causing dimensional instabilities in polymer matrix composite parts have been identified by various authors [1, 2].

The processing of thermoplastic matrix composites, although it does not present the problems of cure shrinkage associated with thermosetting resins, involves effects that influence directly the dimensional stability of the material by introducing internal stresses of varying magnitudes. The principal sources of process-related internal stresses are [3-6]:

- Thermomechanical properties mismatch between constituents
- Thermal skin-core effects
- Morphological skin-core effects (dependent on cooling rate)
- Annealing stresses
- Expansion stress due to volume changes with pressure
- Process-induced matrix orientation
- Process-induced fiber misalignment.

Dimensional instability in composites during their service life, i.e. after processing, is usually linked to the time-dependent "stress management" within a part:

- Changes in the internal stress state
- Stress due to external loading
- Morphology and morphological changes (e.g. recrystallization)
- Changes in the microstructure of the material (e.g. microcracking [4])
- Physical aging (structural relaxation) of the material
- Anisotropy effects (e.g. polymer matrix and/or fiber orientation)
- Material heterogeneity
- Excessive tolerances and deviations from specifications in production.

As can be seen from the conceptual schematic in Figure 1, the determining factors for the dimensional stability of thermoplastic matrix composites can be classified as stress generating, often linked to processing, or as stress relieving, tied to the post-treatment and the service life of the part.

The long-term variations of internal stresses are usually more significant in thermoplastic matrix composites than in thermosetting materials. The absence of crosslinking generally leads to a greater molecular mobility at a given temperature, and thus to shorter relaxation times. This implies more pronounced viscoelastic effects at the service temperature. Furthermore, besides a loss of mobility associated with physical aging of the amorphous phase below the glass transition, one must consider volumetric effects due to aging and to the morphological evolution of the material, when dealing with semicrystalline materials. The volume changes brought about by secondary crystallization, for example 6 % difference between semi-crystalline and amorphous polyethylene terephthalate [7], can be orders of magnitude larger than those caused by physical aging, e.g. 0.03% for polycarbonate, one week after a quench to 45°C [8].

The total magnitudes of dimensional instabilities can range from several centimeters to fractions of a micron, depending on the mechanisms involved and the geometry of the part. Since even the smallest unwanted deformations can have a large influence on the performance of a structure, as is the case in optomechanics, a good understanding of the phenomena involved in the long-term dimensional stability of composites is important.

Analytical models are available to describe dimensional changes in homogeneous as well as multiphase materials such as semicrystalline polymers. These most often lend themselves to the analysis of an isolated phenomenon. A unified model is still needed, however, to account for the various effects contributing to the dimensional stability of composites. Existing experimental methods as well are often highly specialized and thus limited in scope. The results provided by such methods give an essential insight into the different underlying mechanisms. The most direct

Figure 1. The dimensional stability of thermoplastic matrix composites: an overview

conclusions on dimensional stability, however, are derived from the actual deformation of a composite material structure.

Measuring the very small deformations and deformation rates of a composite part over time requires a method with high sensitivity, that causes a minimal amount of disturbance to the sample during the time of the test. Speckle pattern interferometry proves to be a well suited method. The aim of this paper is to present the principles, possibilities, and limitations of the method and its application to the characterization of dimensional instabilities in thermoplastic matrix composites.

2. SPECKLE PATTERN INTERFEROMETRY

2.1. Measurements principles

When an object with a non-optical surface is illuminated by a coherent light source (e.g. a laser), the interference between light waves scattered from different points on the surface gives rise to a spotted, shimmering pattern called the speckle effect. Each bright spot, or speckle, has a continuous intensity distribution [9]; it is uniquely defined and can thus be "traced". The intensity distribution of the speckle varies cyclically as the object is moved toward or away from the light source, since the interference is three-dimensional. Correlating two images (2 positions of the object) gives a set of fringes which describe the displacement and the deformation of the object [10]. One of the main features of ESPI is that it provides a full field measurement of the object's deformation. This makes it more powerful than most other methods, which give only local information on strains or displacements.

2.2. System layout

Recent developments in electronic speckle pattern interferometry (ESPI) have made it a metrological tool that can be used with relative ease and with consistent results. The availability of extremely fast computers has made it possible to record and analyze full images within times that allow an almost real-time evaluation of the results. The photographic plate can, with certain tradeoffs that are discussed below, be replaced by a CCD camera. The acquisition of images in the form of digital data in turn offers the benefits of digital image analysis. The layout of a typical ESPI measurement system for the acquisition of 3-D displacements is shown schematically in Figure 2. With the integrated equipment used in this work, the measurements can be made in three dimensions quasi simultaneously.

Figure 2. Setup for in-plane and out-of-plane ESPI measurements

Figure 3. Spatial resolution and limits of the deformation gradient

2.3. Sensitivity and resolution

The sensitivity and accuracy of ESPI measurements depend on the setup, i.e. the viewing angle, and various system values such as the wavelength λ of the laser, the illumination, and the optical parameters of the viewing system, and on the system used for the digital image processing. Since a displacement parallel to the imaging beam increases the length of the beam's path by twice the displacement, the *out-of-plane* sensitivity corresponds to half the laser's wavelength; the *in-plane* sensitivity is furthermore defined by θ , i.e. half of the angle subtended by the two imaging beams.

$$\text{out-of-plane: } s = \frac{\lambda}{2} \qquad \text{in-plane: } s = \frac{\lambda}{2 \sin \theta} \qquad (1)$$

For a near-IR laser with a wavelength of $0.830 \mu\text{m}$, one fringe is generated by an out-of-plane displacement difference of $0.415 \mu\text{m}$, and by an in-plane relative displacement of $1.0 \mu\text{m}$ ($\theta = 24.5^\circ$)

The spatial resolution and deformation gradients are subject to certain technical limitations. The picture is recorded and stored as an array of 512×512 pixels with 255 shades of gray. The digitalization of the picture causes a loss of resolution that is noticed when the deformation gradients are too large, i.e. the fringes are too close together (Figure 3). This is compounded by the oscillations in the speckle intensity due to variations in the density of the air between the object and the viewing system. Such oscillations especially affect the quality of the measurements during non-isothermal tests, in which excessive heating rates lead to turbulences that introduce large measuring errors. For the present setup, with a 60 mm lens at a distance of 1.0 m, i.e. a width of the viewing field of about 100 mm, the maximum deformation gradient is about 3-4 fringes/10 mm ($\epsilon = 0.016\%$ out-of-plane and $\epsilon = 0.12\%$ in-plane) in isothermal out-of-plane measurements at room temperature.

3. APPLICATION TO THE ANALYSIS OF DIMENSIONAL STABILITY

3.1. Sample and test description

Speckle pattern interferometry was applied to the measurement of very small deformations associated with changes of the internal stress distribution and geometry of cross-ply laminates. A cross-ply laminated beam provides a simple way to investigate the influence of layup on the dimensional stability of a composite [3], since it allows an easy variation of parameters and requires only a one-dimensional analysis. Beams ($100 \text{ mm} \times 16 \text{ mm}$) with varying thicknesses and layups were compression molded at 190°C and 4 MPa from 0.5 mm thick glass fiber-reinforced polypropylene (ICI Plytron®) prepregs with a fiber content of about 35 % by volume and a unidirectional fiber orientation. The samples were cooled under pressure with a cooling rate of $23^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and demolded as soon as the temperature had dropped under 110°C , at which temperature solidification is about complete.

Figure 4. Definition of the variables

Figure 5. Setup for ESPI measurement of long-term deformations at variable temperature

3.2. Test setup

A Newport MP/MV-1000 moiré interferometer with a Sony AVC-D5CE CCD camera was used to measure the initial shape of the samples after demolding. The subsequent, time-dependent deformation of the composite cross-ply laminates due to changes in the internal stress distribution was measured in a setup as sketched in Figure 5 using a Newport HC ESPI system. The image analysis was performed with Breukmann Optocat® software. The deformation rate $d\delta/dt$ was measured for a segment length L of 50 mm (Figure 4) along the centerline of the beam, to avoid edge effects. The range of rates measured goes from 300 nm/s at the beginning of an experiment down to less than 1 nm/s for the longer times. These values were averaged over a measuring window of three seconds to two minutes, respectively. Although the present results are from isothermal tests, the setup also allows non-isothermal tests. As the high sensitivity of ESPI calls for a good vibration isolation in order to ensure a sufficient stability for precise measurements, the entire experimental setup is placed on a pneumatically damped table.

3.3. Results and discussion

The initial internal stress distribution through the thickness of the beams was calculated based on thermal expansion and modulus vs. temperature values obtained from separate experiments and a linear thermoelastic laminate calculation. The calculated stress distributions for the 5-ply laminates are shown in Figure 6. These calculated distributions tended to underestimate the initial curvature of the beams, especially for a higher proportion of plies with a transverse fiber orientation. As is supported by the correspondence between this discrepancy and the higher deformation rates in the rate vs. time plot (Figure 7), this is due to the fact that the curvature was measured only several minutes after demolding, when the sample had already undergone a significant shape change.

Figure 6. Internal stress distribution for the 5-ply layups tested (// : axial plies, ⊥ transverse plies)

Figure 7. Deformation rate $d\delta/dt$ vs. time for various 5-ply layups tested.

Figure 8. Deformation rate $d\delta/dt$ vs. time for the $(90^0_4, 0^0_1)$ layup.

The deformation rate as a function of time for various layups is reported in Figure 7. The direction of deformation is determined by the internal stress distribution (Figure 6), and the rate is governed by the stress level and the structural stiffness at any given time. When the outermost fiber of the transverse layers of the beam is under compression, the beam's curvature increases as the stress decreases (positive values of the deformation rate); the opposite is true for beams with a tensile stress in the outermost fiber. The structural stiffness of the beam and thus the time-dependent position of its neutral axis furthermore change as the stresses in the material relax, i.e. as the observed modulus decreases. This, along with the stress level in the section and the material viscoelastic response, affects the rate of redistribution of the stresses and thus the shape of the beam. The result can be a type of "flip-flop" behavior, as the direction of deformation changes. For example, the $(90_3, 0_2)$ layup experiences a reversal in the direction of deformation, as the outermost fiber in the transverse layer, which is at first under compression, finds itself under tension after the material has somewhat "relaxed". The beam first becomes more warped and then flattens out again.

A $\log(\text{rate})$ vs. $\log(\text{time})$ plot of the data (Figure 8) shows that the derivative of the rate of deformation of the samples varies. This feature is most likely also related to the internal stress level and distribution. The curve can be divided into three regimes: a first, with a relatively constant decrease of the deformation rate, a second, with a lower slope, and a third in which the derivative of the deformation rate decreases again. A fourth or more regimes are not excluded, although they were not observed over the test duration in this series of experiments. The change in the slope of the deformation rate suggests that the deformation may be subject to competing processes. Some of

Figure 9. Part of the solution to dimensional instability problems is based on characterizing where, between creep and stress relaxation, the loading history of the material is situated.

the processes contributing to the viscoelastic deformation have taken place at the time of transition between two regimes, while others are continuing. The piecewise linear nature of the curves points to a power law dependence of the deformation rate on time. This can be related to the power-law nature of the material behavior which was observed for Plytron® in separate uniaxial stress relaxation tests. The change in the derivative of the rate, i.e. of the power law exponent, reflects shifts in the stress-dependent relaxation times of the composite and thus variations in the processes involved in the viscoelastic deformation of the material.

Concerning the material response, an important point is that the viscoelastic effects responsible for the change of shape of the samples studied do not occur in a single mode, as is usually the case in material testing. Examining a small region of material in the beam, one sees that it is subject to some amount of stress relaxation, but also to an ongoing deformation with a variable rate. Its stress/strain history therefore corresponds to a loading condition between the idealized extremes of creep and stress relaxation. Considering this, a question that reveals to be central to the problem is whether the dimensional stability of composite parts can be examined within the framework of creep deformation or stress relaxation, or yet a time-varying combination of these two extremes (Figure 9). Creep is basically a system subject to continuous energy input with rates varying according to the velocity (deformation rate) of the process. Relaxation, on the other hand, is a constant energy system, with a one-time energy input that is dissipated as the material relaxes. The actual path which is followed, indicated by a question mark in Figure 9, depends on the material behavior and especially on the structural characteristics of the composite part.

In a more general perspective, the principal factors affecting the deformations within a composite part loaded only by internal stresses are the fiber orientation distribution and its spatial variation through the part. These affect not only the material properties and the buildup of the internal stresses, but also the time-dependent structural stiffness of the part, which determines how the stresses are dissipated. This influence of the fiber orientation variation through the thickness can be investigated qualitatively by studying the warped shape of disk samples, in which the topography of the warped shape is a function of the fiber orientation distribution.

4. FURTHER APPLICATION POSSIBILITIES

The very high sensitivity and the full-field capability of ESPI makes it suitable for detecting flaws in composite samples subjected to mechanical loading [11]. Dimensional instabilities due to the development of delaminations and subsurface cracks can be monitored inasmuch as they give rise to deformation fields at the surface of the object. ESPI can also be applied to the measurement of the thermal expansion of polymers and composites with temperature differentials of only 1-2°C, and to tracking dimensional changes due to morphological changes such as recrystallization and physical aging. Work is in progress in these various applications.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The ESPI measuring system provides the high sensitivity necessary to measure the extremely small deformations associated with dimensional instabilities in fiber-reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites. Since no contact to the sample is necessary, it avoids the disturbances caused to the sample with methods such as strain gauges and other electromechanical displacement sensors. When used together with moiré interferometry, it gives a measuring range going from the order of several millimeters down to fractions of a micron.

The measurement of the change of shape of a cross-ply beam due to internal stresses has shown that the dimensional stability is determined not only by constituent material properties, but also by the microscopic stress distribution due to the fiber microstructure and the structural stiffness of the part. The latter in fact determines the flow conditions to which the material is subjected, between the extremes of creep and relaxation. Any model describing the long-term, time-dependent deformation of a composite part should reflect this fact.

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7. REFERENCES

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